

IMPROVED TREATMENT OF PURULENT SOFT TISSUE WOUNDS OF THE EXTREMITIES USING PHYSICOCHEMICAL TECHNIQUES AND PROLONGED LAVAGE

Mirsoliyev Shakhzod Gulomovich
Abu Ali ibn Sina Bukhara State Medical Institute

Background. Purulent soft tissue wounds of the extremities remain a major challenge in modern surgery due to their high incidence, prolonged treatment periods, and frequent development of infectious complications. The search for effective methods that accelerate wound cleansing and tissue repair remains an important task in clinical practice.

Objective. To evaluate the clinical effectiveness of an improved treatment method for purulent soft tissue wounds of the extremities based on physicochemical techniques and prolonged lavage.

Materials and Methods. A total of 113 patients with purulent soft tissue diseases of the upper and lower extremities were examined. The control group consisted of 65 patients treated between 2020 and 2024 using conventional therapy, including surgical debridement, antiseptic wound sanitation with 25% dimexide solution, water-soluble ointments, detoxification therapy, and standard postoperative care. The main group included 48 patients treated between 2025 and 2026. In addition to conventional treatment, these patients underwent ultrasonic wound treatment followed by prolonged lavage with a 25% dimexide solution using a specially developed device. Clinical efficacy was assessed using wound cleansing dynamics, inflammatory response, granulation tissue formation, bacteriological findings, wound healing rate, and duration of hospitalization.

Results. The use of physicochemical techniques combined with prolonged lavage provided more effective elimination of necrotic tissue and reduction of microbial contamination compared with conventional treatment. Patients in the main group demonstrated earlier wound cleansing, faster granulation tissue formation, accelerated epithelialization, and improved local wound conditions. The proposed method contributed to a reduction in inflammatory manifestations and shortened the duration

of inpatient treatment. Clinical observations also revealed improved wound healing dynamics and a lower incidence of wound-related complications.

Conclusion. The combination of physicochemical wound treatment and prolonged lavage represents an effective approach for managing purulent soft tissue wounds of the extremities. The proposed method enhances wound sanitation, promotes reparative processes, reduces treatment duration, and improves overall clinical outcomes. Its implementation in surgical practice may increase the effectiveness of treatment and rehabilitation of patients with purulent soft tissue infections.

Keywords: purulent wounds, soft tissue infection, extremities, prolonged lavage, physicochemical treatment, wound healing, surgical infection, ultrasound therapy.

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